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Emotional Intelligence as a Stimulator of Technology Strategy for Business Success

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Effective improvement and execution of technologies require incredibly careful consideration not only to technological and engineering advancements and resulting capabilities, but also to human, raw materials, financial feasibility, and the reasonably competitive environment. The strategic management of technology (SMT) brings together engineering, scientific, and management disciplines to tackle the preparation, growth, and implementation of technical skills to form and serve a strategic and a functional purpose of a business.

Technology operates as an important trigger for emotional responses, because of its novelty, ability and social function. Examining emotions has been a subject that has been highly studied in fields such as psychology, sociology, but more recently it has become an investigation process of organizational behavior because of increasing emphasis on examining specifically how emotions interact with success [1]. The concept of emotional intelligence (EI) can help employees grow into better team players, show more ingenuity in their work, and increase overall performance through the highly effective techniques of integrating working environment and implementation of EI [2]. Emotional intelligence integrates a wide range of skills that explain how individuals handle emotions and can be a factor in enhancing the relationship between SMT and organizational performance (OP). The major gap in past research is the inadequacy of exploring the relationships between EI, SMT, and OP.

Since the service sector is more closely related to the human factor, SMT and OP will play an important role in EI. Hence, an empirical investigation covering the main commercial banks operating in Sri Lanka was undertaken with the key decision makers who are making strategic decisions. As the current study is conducted in the banks registered under Colombo Stock Exchange the information collected and the results from the research can be used to define whether testing for EI is an important tool when enrolling new employees, promoting employees and in identification of talents and succession planning towards the OP.

The study found the importance of EI to the relationship between SMT and OP to the practitioner. Hence, the necessary actions can be taken to increase level of EI of the organizations. Since the study found that EI positively affect OP, the managers should analyze, provide clear guidelines, and communicate to ensure the importance of EI to build better employer, employee,

and customer relationships to increase the OP. Furthermore, managers must spend time to confirm the progress of EI of their subordinates. Managers need to realize the importance of SMT and EI applications in adding value to their work, as well as EI's potential to improve SMT's relationship with OP. An important aspect is the growth of the expertise and decision-making skills of technology-related employees. That goal can be accomplished through the implementation of EI-related programs that emphasize the capacity of employee decision-making and growth, including managers. Managers should always increase the strength of the feelings of subordinates in the sense of competence through their willingness to accept and respond to the concerns of their juniors.

Further, the managers should be mindful to gain skill in their subordinates to achieve the benefits in each dimension of EI. Managers should have EI skills so that they can help their colleagues develop EI. In addition, the juniors should be taught about the method of coping with the emotional issue and how their supervisors can communicate with others. Managers should also create an enjoyable working environment by holding group discussions to give subordinates an opportunity to interact simultaneously. Thus, the feeling of empathy could be cultivated, and the subordinates can recognize the feelings of their colleagues and receive input based on their reaction. Managers also can reduce the anxiety problem between subordinates by helping them to reduce low self-efficacy level and the ability or technique to reduce their anxiety should be offered to juniors to facilitate endurance.

Since results showed that SMT positively affects OP, the management needs regular coaching of technology. Managers need to embark on a regular personalized coaching program to develop all managers' technology skills, which will help them make sound decisions. Coaching programs can be designed to develop the manager's technology expertise so that they can assess and decide on strategies and investments where digital technology is key, decide on major technology investments including the innovations and what budgets are needed and whether the organization can invest in technology start-ups, assess and authorize partnerships. A deeper insight of how to make management programs for technology to become more successful could be gained by connecting EI to the learning concepts of the organization and technology. The consequence is the consideration of EI competencies in recruiting, retaining staff in addition to the designing and implementation of advanced EI training programs.

Furthermore, the findings led to conclude that in recruiting new managers, organizations should use management approaches that go beyond merely measuring IQ levels and technical competencies. The board of recruitment should consider the EI competencies. Having a high EI will help managers build healthy and trusting relationships with their subordinates, better understand others, and perceive other actions more easily. Hence, programs of EI awareness are also required for every employee including managers to unravel the core competencies of the EI such as self-confidence, trustworthiness, competence, adaptability, motivation, team building and leadership abilities, stress management, etc. Evaluation of EI of the existing organizational employees should be introduced. It is equally important to measure the EI level of the current employees and the managers of an organization, so that the employees with higher EI are assigned

matching roles. Emotional Intelligence based KPIs can be introduced for managers and can be measured over time to assess the level of improvements.

Training sessions of EI, for managers is recommended and also required to monitor the association of EI with performance drivers such as customer satisfaction, lower-level employee's satisfaction, customer churn and care management in a technology-based organization and the need for a service operation with a human touch. Conducting trainings of EI can be included to the KPI of organizations as a motivation factor.

The current findings have added value to the model of service-profit chain in service marketing as EI is a critical moderator or a promoter that can manipulate the level OP through a technology strategy. The EI of the employees of the service providers in the service environment is vital as it relates to the quality of service and performance, and this is linked to back-office operations as well. Thus, EI can be a facilitator and in developing people-oriented technology strategy. The major contribution of the study is the EI moderation theory between SMT's relationship and OP. The current study adds empirical support that both SMT and EI need to be involved and work together to be successful, towards the organizational performance.

References:

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